

A Markov Random Field approach for Topology-Preserving Registration: application to Object-Based Tomographic Image Interpolation

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Abstract

This paper proposes a topology-preserving multiresolution elastic registration method based on a discrete Markov random field of deformations and a block-matching procedure. The method is applied to the object-based interpolation of tomographic slices. For that purpose, the fidelity of a given deformation to the data is established by a block-matching strategy based on intensity and gradient related features, the smoothness of the transformation is favored by an appropriate prior on the field and the deformation is guaranteed to maintain the topology by imposing some hard-constraints on the local configurations of the field. The resulting deformation is defined as the maximum a posteriori configuration of the field. Additionally, the relative influence of the fidelity and smoothness terms is weighted by the unsupervised estimation of the field parameters. In order to obtain an unbiased interpolation result, the registration is

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performed both in the forward and backward directions and the resulting transformations are combined by using the local information content of the deformation. The method is applied to Magnetic Resonance and Computed Tomography acquisitions of the brain and the torso. Quantitative comparisons offer an overall improvement of performance with respect to related works in the literature. Additionally, the application of the interpolation method to cardiac Magnetic Resonance images has shown that the removal of any of the main components of the algorithm results in a decrease in performance which has proven to be statistically significant.

Index Terms

Markov random field, parameter estimation, tomography interpolation, topology-preserving registration.

I. INTRODUCTION

Image registration is concerned with the search of an optimal transformation for the alignment between objects in (at least) two images. It has many applications in imaging, such as fusion of image information [1], material points tracking [2], atlas construction [3] or object-based interpolation of contiguous slices [4], [5], which is the application domain that we focus on in this paper.

Mathematically, let I_0 and I_1 be a pair of images. The registration problem may be posed as finding a spatial transformation φ so that every point in I_0 is matched to a point in I_1 . Image registration can be formulated as the minimization in the space of possible transformations of an energy function H ; i.e., the registration looks for the optimal transformation φ^* that satisfies $\varphi^* = \underset{\varphi}{\operatorname{argmin}} H(\varphi)$. Usually, the energy function H takes on the form

$$H(\varphi) = \int_{\Omega} [f(I_0(\mathbf{r}), I_1(\varphi(\mathbf{r}))) + g(\varphi(\mathbf{r}))] d\mathbf{r}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{r} denotes a spatial location and Ω is the integration domain of the problem. The functions $f(\cdot, \cdot)$ and $g(\cdot)$ refer, respectively, to a data fidelity term that accounts for the similarity between both images for a given transformation and to a regularization term that favors the smoothness of the deformation. Different registration problems entail different choices for f and g and different assumptions on the transformation φ . For instance, when dealing with intramodality image registration f can be based on the squared difference or the normalized correlation of the image intensities. On the other hand, for intermodality image registration, f usually is based on a measure of the joint information content of

the images, such as mutual information¹. Regarding the assumptions on the transformation, different registration scenarios emerge in the rigid and deformable cases. A small number of parameters serves to determine the global transformation in the former, whereas in the latter, which is the one we are concerned with here, the degrees of freedom and complexity of the problem increase considerably. In this case, g can favor those solutions in which the first or second order derivatives of the displacement field tend to zero (membrane or plate-like solutions) or can be based on a biomechanical model of deformation.

Without any further requirements on the deformation field, the solution to (1) can result in unrealistic transformations, so a proper set of additional constraints should be introduced in the problem such as continuity, differentiability, topology preservation (i.e., preservation of the connectivity and neighborhood relationships of the image objects) as well as unbiasedness (i.e., insensitivity of the solution with the change of the image roles). Indeed, this paper is focused on the insertion of the topology preservation constraint in a discrete stochastic formulation based on a Markov random field (MRF) of deformations and a block-matching procedure. The other constraints (continuity, differentiability and unbiasedness) are also considered in our method. Nevertheless, in a discrete setting, the continuity and differentiability constraints depend on the interpolation functions used to recover the continuous deformation fields, which in turn can affect the topology preservation. Regarding the unbiasedness constraint, an indirect approach is adopted. Since our registration method is applied to the interpolation of contiguous slices in tomographic images, we obtain a pair of transformations by interchanging the roles of the moving and target images in the registration step and to introduce the constraint in the interpolation step so the overall result of the algorithm is unbiased. Moreover, the stochastic formulation provides not only a solution of the registration problem, but also a measure of its uncertainty, so it is possible to perform an appropriate combination of the intensities of the images coming from the two computed transformations using this information. Another advantage of this framework is the existence of techniques to estimate the relative influence of the fidelity and the smoothness terms in the energy functional and thus to improve the adaptability of the solutions and the possibility to apply high performance combinatorial optimization techniques [7].

Our stochastic formulation of the registration problem presents some advantages if we consider other topology-preserving probabilistic approaches. As we discuss in Section II-A, the topology preservation proposed in [8] introduces a bias in the registration solution, whereas the MRF-based approach in [9] does not incorporate the model parameters to the Bayesian estimation framework as ours does. Besides,

¹Strictly speaking, the mutual information metric cannot be written in the form given in (1). Nevertheless, it admits some approximations which allow its incorporation to the energy minimization based registration framework [6].

the topology preserving constraint established in the latter work imposes substantial restrictions to the structure of feasible configurations of the field. Finally, considering the overall interpolation scheme, a quantitative comparison shows that our proposal outperforms the so far proposed registration-based interpolation methods [4], [5].

In Section II, we review the proposals that impose some of the aforementioned constraints in the registration problem as well as the approaches for registration-based interpolation to justify the pertinence of the method proposed in this paper. The registration and the interpolation steps of the method are respectively described in Sections III and IV. In Section V, we present the results of the interpolation. They include a quantitative comparison with state of the art methods such as [5], [4] following the methodology in [10], a justification of the benefits provided by the algorithm and a set of examples to visually assess the performance and limitations of the method. Finally, some conclusions and remarks are presented in Section VI, together with possible extensions of the work.

II. BACKGROUND

This Section is divided into three parts. First, a critical review of constrained registration methods is presented in Section II-A. Second, the registration-based interpolation problem, which turns to be an interesting application for the validation of different registration methods, is introduced in Section II-B. Third, the main attributes of our method are enumerated in Section II-C.

A. Constraints on the deformation

Many registration methods consider the constraints introduced in Section I. A seminal work which defines the registration problem as such of finding a homeomorphic map, i.e., a continuous bijective transformation whose inverse is also continuous, is the one in [11]. The registration is defined as the solution of a viscous-fluid Partial Differential Equation (PDE). This formulation can deal with large deformations while simultaneously preserving the topology. The solution of the PDE is implemented by a Finite Element (FE) method, which involves a large computational load, mainly due to the successive spatial over-relaxation steps. Additionally, it is necessary to reinitialize the discretization grid to prevent from singularities in the transformation.

The large deformation diffeomorphic metric mapping (LDDMM) framework, reviewed in [12], poses the registration problem as the computation of a geodesic path on the manifold of diffeomorphisms connecting the images. A diffeomorphism is defined as a differentiable bijective transformation with differentiable inverse. This method is formulated by a variational problem similar to (1), but instead of

regularizing the deformation field, it regularizes the temporal flow of a velocity vector field, which is integrated to provide the solution. One advantage of this method in comparison with [11] is that the velocity fields are smooth not only in space, but also in time. Some interesting features of this algorithm are that the solution is not only the deformation but also the path connecting the images and that it implicitly provides a measure of the distance between two images connected by a diffeomorphic map. Extensions of the basic LDDMM framework have been developed to include an affine transformation component [13], to obtain symmetric or unbiased transformations [14] or to reduce the computation requirements [15]. Diffeomorphic extensions have also been proposed for the popular Demons algorithm, with an advantage in computational efficiency [16].

On the other hand, some methods are not based on a physical model of deformation, but on its parametric representation. For instance, simple approaches based on B-splines preserve the topology by restricting the maximum deformation taking into account the spacing of the grid [17], whereas more sophisticated methods impose restrictions on the coefficients of the transformation [18].

Our proposal differs from the previous approaches in that it embodies the registration problem in a stochastic framework. Hence, it has more in common with methodologies such as [8], where the registration solution is obtained as the maximum a posteriori (MAP) of a field of deformations whose prior favors the smoothness of the solution simultaneously ensuring one-to-one mappings and whose likelihood tends to improve the fidelity of the solution to the data. The major drawback in [8] is that the smoothness is biased with respect to the chosen diagonal direction of the triangulation [19], [20]. Another stochastic approach for the registration problem is presented in [9], which adopts a discrete Bayesian framework by a MRF of deformations. However, this work does not take advantage of all the inferential capabilities of the Bayesian framework to estimate the parameters of the model. Besides, a simple diffeomorphic constraint is established by limiting the relation between the grid spacing and the maximum deformation, the same as in [17]. Specifically, diffeomorphisms are guaranteed by limiting the maximum deformation to be 0.4 times the grid spacing, which limits either the resolution of the field or the range of allowed displacements beyond what is necessary. In contrast to this approach, the range of allowed displacements of our method is not restricted by the grid spacing, but by the configurations in the neighborhood of the site under consideration.

B. Object-based interpolation

Interpolation techniques fall into two main categories: (1) *Scene-based interpolation*, which only uses the intensity of the images and (2) *Object-based interpolation* which uses the spatial correspondence

between the points in different images [10] to interpolate. Traditional interpolation methods (nearest-neighbor, linear, cubic,...) belong to the first category. Object-based interpolation can be further divided into methods that operate on features extracted from the image and methods that operate on the image intensities directly [5]. Feature extraction could involve, for instance, a previous segmentation in order to match the structures of interest in the images. The analysis of the literature shows that object-based techniques generally improve the interpolation quality of scene-based counterparts [10], [5], [4], but with an important increase in computational load.

First works on object-based interpolation operated on binary data [21], [22], so they required a previous segmentation of the structure of interest from the background. The idea is to compute a distance transform of the boundaries of the structure, then to interpolate the distance values by any scene-based method and finally to recover a binary image by zero-thresholding. This idea is extended in [23] to interpolate grey-level images and additional efforts have developed a set of morphology-based interpolation methods (see [24] as an example).

Another strategy for interslice interpolation is to use image intensities directly, so the object information is considered implicitly. The key idea is to perform a registration step that builds a deformation field between the pair of 2D images and then to perform the interpolation based on the obtained deformation. This strategy has been successfully adopted since the early work in [25] which, favoring small deformations, performs a matching of adjacent slices based on the similarity of local structures in terms of intensity, gradient magnitude and gradient direction. These terms, which make up the cost function, are weighted empirically and an inverse-consistency restriction is added to the procedure (which has been subsequently refined in [26]). The advantage of a registration-based interpolation technique is that the existing work on registration of medical images can be used to perform the interpolation. As stated in [5], supposing that the adopted registration methodology is able to recover the desired transformation, the basic assumption of registration-based interpolation is that adjacent slices contain similar anatomical features. Otherwise, when a structure appearing in one image disappears in the other, the advantages of registration will be lost.

Some examples of registration-based interpolation methods have emerged in the last decade. The aforementioned proposal, [5], uses a spline-based registration method for interpolation. Mutual information between the images is taken as the registration metric. This is a controversial choice, since mutual information is better suited for intermodality registration [1]. Nonetheless, the method in [27] uses a block-matching procedure based on intensity, gradient magnitude and gradient direction differences between the images, with similar results. In [4] optical flow is used for interpolation. The transformation

is computed twice by interchanging the roles of the fixed and moving images and results are combined in the interpolation stage, which constitutes an advantage with respect to [5]. The method incorporates a set of refinements to improve the performance and efficiency of the interpolation. These include a multiresolution approach, a discretization of the deformation space in order to compress the information that matches both images and a combination of the transforms obtained by multiple image pairs to perform the interpolation. However, this method has two important limitations. On one hand, the optical flow approximation is unable to cope with large deformations, usually appearing in the case of large slice separation. On the other hand, the parameters that influence the refinements performed must be empirically tuned.

Comparisons between the methods in [5] and [4] were performed in [4] following the methodology suggested in [10]. A better performance is obtained with the optical flow-based method [4] when the error between interpolated and real images was compared in terms of the mean square difference (MSD). Nevertheless, the opposite occurs when the comparative is established in terms of the number of sites of disagreement (NSD) metric, as defined in [10], in which case the method in [5] outperforms the one in [4]². In this paper, we will also use the methodology of [10] to show that our proposal outperforms both [5] and [4] either considering MSD or NSD metrics.

C. Remarkable attributes of the proposal

The main features of our registration-based interpolation method are summarized below:

- The registration is based on a multiresolution decomposition of the image and the deformation.
- The fidelity of a given deformation to the data is established by novel intensity and gradient related features in a block-matching strategy.
- The smoothness of the transformation is favored by an appropriate prior on the field.
- The deformation is guaranteed to maintain the topology by imposing some hard-constraints on the local configurations of the field, which is a novel contribution in MRF-based registration and an important contribution of this paper.
- The deformation solution for each resolution level is stated as the MAP of a MRF.
- The parameters of the field are updated in an unsupervised fashion by alternating between parameter estimation and optimization of the field. This is rarely implemented in registration procedures and allows for an adaptive weighting of the fidelity and smoothness terms.

²We should also mention [28], which uses an adaptive context-finding procedure to improve the interpolation; the paper claims to outperform [4] but conducted comparisons are partial.

- The registration is performed both in the forward and backward directions and the interpolation combines the intensities derived from both transformations, so the whole procedure is unbiased.
- The intensities are combined by means of a local information measure of the deformations obtained, which is also a novel contribution of the method. This allows to diminish the worsening in performance provoked by changes of the structures contained in contiguous slices.

III. REGISTRATION METHOD

We are given a pair of zero-origin 2D discrete-space images $I_i^0[\mathbf{m}] = I_i(\mathbf{m}\Delta_{\mathbf{m}}^0)$, with $i \in \{0, 1\}$ denoting each of the images and $\Delta_{\mathbf{m}}^0$ the pixel resolution. From this pair, a set of images at different resolution levels is built by subsampling the original images by a factor of 2, $I_i^l[\mathbf{m}] = I_i^0[2^l\mathbf{m}]$, with $l \in \{0, \dots, L-1\}$ denoting the resolution level and L the total number of levels. Thus, we have $\Delta_{\mathbf{m}}^l = 2^l\Delta_{\mathbf{m}}^0$.

The registration objective is to estimate a transformation $\varphi_{0 \rightarrow 1}^0 : \Omega \rightarrow \Omega$ that maps the domain of I_0 onto the domain of I_1 . The transformation can be related with the displacement map \mathbf{u} by

$$\varphi(\mathbf{r}) = \mathbf{r} + \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}). \quad (2)$$

For a given resolution level l , the algorithm starts with the estimated displacement map for the previous level $\bar{\mathbf{u}}^l = \mathbf{u}^{l+1}$, with $\mathbf{u}^L = \mathbf{0}$, estimates the residual displacement $\hat{\mathbf{u}}^l$, adds it to the initial displacement $\mathbf{u}^l = \bar{\mathbf{u}}^l + \hat{\mathbf{u}}^l$ and propagates the result to the next level. The estimation is performed in a discrete set of spatial positions or *sites* \mathbf{s} , $\varphi^l[\mathbf{s}] = \varphi^l(\mathbf{s}\Delta_{\mathbf{s}}^l)$, with $\Delta_{\mathbf{s}}^l$ the transformation resolution at the scale l , which satisfies the relation $\Delta_{\mathbf{s}}^l = 2^l\Delta_{\mathbf{s}}^0$. The reconstruction of the continuous transformation is obtained by bilinear interpolation of the values of the transformation in the sites. Moreover, the feasible residual displacements take on values in the space of quantized transformations $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{k}}^l = \mathbf{k}\Delta_{\mathbf{k}}^l$, with $\Delta_{\mathbf{k}}^l$ the quantization step at the resolution l , which also satisfies $\Delta_{\mathbf{k}}^l = 2^l\Delta_{\mathbf{k}}^0$. The key idea of these discretizations for a given resolution level is represented in Fig. 1, where the possible displacements for a given site are added to the displacement from the previous level $\bar{\mathbf{u}}^l$.

Therefore, we search for a continuous transformation $\varphi : \Omega \rightarrow \Omega$, such that φ maps the boundary of Ω onto itself and that is locally injective, that is to say

$$J(\mathbf{r}) = \left| \frac{\partial \varphi(\mathbf{r})}{\partial \mathbf{r}} \right| > 0 \quad \forall \mathbf{r} \in \Omega, \quad (3)$$

so it is a topology-preserving or homeomorphic map [29]. The continuity of the transformation is ensured by the bilinear interpolation scheme of the deformations in the grid of sites whereas the identical

Fig. 1. Discretization of the model for a given resolution level and previous displacement $\bar{\mathbf{u}}^l[\mathbf{s}]$. Image pixels are represented as line intersections, transformation sites as circles, and transformation values for the site \mathbf{s} as crosses.

mapping of the boundary is ensured by establishing a zero-deformation Dirichlet boundary condition on the deformation field. The positivity of the Jacobian is somewhat more subtle, as it was anticipated in Section II-A and is treated later on.

For each resolution level l , a MRF [30] is built by defining a field of discrete random variables $\mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{s}}$ over the grid sites $\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}$ which take on values in the space of quantized deformations $\mathbf{k} \in \mathcal{K}$ such that $|\mathbf{k}\Delta_{\mathbf{k}}^0| \leq \frac{1}{K^{L-1}}u_{\max}$, with $\frac{2^l}{K^{L-1-l}}u_{\max}$ denoting the maximum allowed deformation for level l , $K \geq 1$ a constant to accelerate the algorithm (under the assumption that the coarser level solution is close to the finer level solution), and $|\cdot|$ the vector magnitude. The MRF is built from the definition of a system of contextual dependencies over the geometry of the sites. These dependencies are encoded in the form of a neighborhood system $\delta(\mathbf{s})$. A customary way to define the neighborhood system is by means of the order of the neighborhood which is the smallest integer b that satisfies $b \geq |\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{s}'|^2$, where $\mathbf{s}' \in \delta(\mathbf{s})$.

The Hammersley-Clifford theorem [31] states that if a Random Field is a MRF for the neighborhood δ , it is also a Gibbs Random Field (GRF) for that neighborhood and vice versa. In a GRF we have the relationship

$$\Pi(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{Z} \exp(-H(\mathbf{x})), \quad (4)$$

which models the probability of occurrence of a configuration of the field $\Pi(\mathbf{x})$ as the negative exponential of the energy of that configuration $H(\mathbf{x})$ normalized by Z , the so-called *partition function*, which is given

by

$$Z = \sum_{\mathbf{z}} \exp(-H(\mathbf{z})). \quad (5)$$

From a Bayesian perspective, given the image pair (I_0, I_1) , one has to consider the posterior field

$$\Pi(\mathbf{x} \mid I_0, I_1) \propto \Pi(\mathbf{x})f(I_0, I_1 \mid \mathbf{x}). \quad (6)$$

which is also Markovian and where $f(I_0, I_1 \mid \mathbf{x})$ is known as the *likelihood* function of the data given a configuration of the field and $\Pi(\mathbf{x})$ is a prior model for the field. In order to define the posterior field, one has to consider a functional form for its energy function $H(\mathbf{x}; I_0, I_1)$, which is developed just below.

A. Design of the field

The energy function $H(\mathbf{x}; I_0, I_1)$ for the posterior field is obtained as the sum of four potential terms

$$\begin{aligned} H(\mathbf{x}; I_0, I_1) = & \sigma_0 \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{C}_1} V_1(x_{\mathbf{s}}; I_0, I_1) + \sigma_1 \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{C}_1} V_1(x_{\mathbf{s}}; |\nabla_M I_0|, |\nabla_M I_1|) + \\ & \lambda \sum_{(\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2) \in \mathcal{C}_2} V_2(x_{\mathbf{s}_1}, x_{\mathbf{s}_2}) + \beta \sum_{(\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2, \mathbf{s}_3) \in \mathcal{C}_3} V_3(x_{\mathbf{s}_1}, x_{\mathbf{s}_2}, x_{\mathbf{s}_3}). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

These terms correspond respectively to the likelihood of the data intensity, the likelihood of the data gradient magnitude, the prior for deformation smoothness and the prior for topology preservation. The first three terms are in the spirit of (1) and the work in [9], whereas the fourth term is the main contribution of our work. Note that the functional form V_1 of the likelihood terms is the same for both of them but the first depends on the image intensities whereas the second depends on the gradient magnitude computed by convolving the images with a Gaussian kernel M whose standard deviation is σ_M , applying a discrete differential operator and taking the magnitude of the result. The potentials are weighted by four parameters σ_0 , σ_1 , λ and β and are defined over the *clique* categories given by \mathcal{C}_1 (for the first two potential terms), \mathcal{C}_2 and \mathcal{C}_3 . A clique \mathcal{C} is defined as a subset of the neighborhood system δ either with a single element or in which every pair of different elements are neighbors [32], with \mathcal{C}_n denoting n -element cliques.

In order to implement this energy function, the method considers a neighborhood system of order $b = 2$, which is plotted in Fig. 2, together with the cliques belonging to each clique category. Just below, we present a description of the potential terms and clarify the meaning of the cliques in Fig. 2. For that purpose, let $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{n}}$ denote a spatial shift of \mathbf{n} pixels, $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{s}}$ the location of the site \mathbf{s} and $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}}}$ the transformed location that corresponds to the local configuration $x_{\mathbf{s}} = \mathbf{k}$:

$$\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}}} = \varphi_{\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}}}^l = \mathbf{s}\Delta_{\mathbf{s}}^l + \overline{\mathbf{u}}^l[\mathbf{s}] + \mathbf{k}\Delta_{\mathbf{k}}^l \quad \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{s}} = \mathbf{s}\Delta_{\mathbf{s}}^l \quad \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{n}} = \mathbf{n}\Delta_{\mathbf{m}}^l. \quad (8)$$

Abusing of notation, we may write $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}} \oplus \mathbf{n}} = \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}}} + \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{n}}$ and $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{s} \oplus \mathbf{n}} = \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{s}} + \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{n}}$. Finally, let continuous image values be obtained by bilinear interpolation.

Fig. 2. Neighborhood system and clique categories of the MRF. a) Neighborhood system. b) 1-element clique. c) 2-element cliques. d) 3-element cliques. See also the orientation of the coordinate system $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2\}$ such that $\mathbf{r} = r_1\mathbf{e}_1 + r_2\mathbf{e}_2$.

1) *Likelihood terms:* The potential function V_1 is computed as:

$$V_1(x_{\mathbf{s}}; F_0^j, F_1^j) = \sum_{|\mathbf{n}| \leq \rho} N[\mathbf{n}] \frac{|F_0^j(\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{s} \oplus \mathbf{n}}) - F_1^j(\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}} \oplus \mathbf{n}})|}{|F_0^j(\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{s} \oplus \mathbf{n}})| + |F_1^j(\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}} \oplus \mathbf{n}})|}, \quad (9)$$

where ρ is the maximum radius of a ball that defines the block from which the image information is extracted and N is a Gaussian kernel with standard deviation $\sigma_N = \frac{\rho - 1}{2}$, so the influence of pixels with $|\mathbf{n}| > \rho$ is negligible. Finally, F_i^j represents the feature j extracted from the image i , respectively $F_i^0 = I_i$ and $F_i^1 = |\nabla_M I_i|$ for the first and second terms in (7).

The functional form in (9) states the fidelity between two image blocks under the local transformation induced by $x_{\mathbf{s}}$ as the Normalized Mean Absolute Difference (NMAD) windowed by a Gaussian kernel in order to improve the contribution of those pixels closer to positions $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{s}}$ and $\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}}}$. The fidelity is encoded into 1-element cliques (see Fig. 2.b), since it only depends on the local transformation as given by $x_{\mathbf{s}}$.

2) *Smoothness term:* The smoothness term is encoded into 2-element cliques, as shown in Fig. 2.c, in order to approximate the deformation gradient by finite differences of order one in both directions of the grid. The prior penalizes those deformations in which $\left| \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial r_1} \right|$ or $\left| \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial r_2} \right|$ are large, with r_1 and r_2 denoting the spatial coordinates $(r_1, r_2) = \mathbf{r}$:

$$V_2(x_{\mathbf{s}_1}, x_{\mathbf{s}_2}) = \frac{|\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}_2}} - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{k}_{\mathbf{s}_1}}|}{|\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{s}_2} - \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{s}_1}|}. \quad (10)$$

Though one can also extract diagonal 2-element cliques from a neighborhood of order $b = 2$, the corresponding potential terms have been set to zero for the sake of computational efficiency.

3) *Topology-preserving term:* As pointed in Section II-A, in contrast to [9], the topology-preservation is guaranteed by an appropriate potential term in the local configurations of the field. Specifically, this term is built upon 3-element cliques, as shown in Fig. 2.d. Note that the four 3-element cliques defined in Fig. 2.d are analogous to the four corners from which the Jacobian is computed in [19] and in Appendix A.

In this case, the relative spatial locations of the clique elements influence the definition of the potential. Let \mathbf{s}_2 be the element in the vertex that subtends the right angle of the triangle formed by the locations

of the clique elements, s_1 the vertex where the non-diagonal edge is along the direction \mathbf{e}_1 and s_3 the vertex where the non-diagonal edge is along the direction \mathbf{e}_2 (see Fig. 2.d). Then, the potential term is constructed by restricting the Jacobian of the deformation in the triangle as follows

$$V(x_{s_1}, x_{s_2}, x_{s_3}) = U \left(\frac{(r_{1, \mathbf{k}_{s_2}} - r_{1, \mathbf{k}_{s_1}})(r_{2, \mathbf{k}_{s_2}} - r_{2, \mathbf{k}_{s_3}}) - (r_{2, \mathbf{k}_{s_2}} - r_{2, \mathbf{k}_{s_1}})(r_{1, \mathbf{k}_{s_2}} - r_{1, \mathbf{k}_{s_3}})}{(r_{1, s_2} - r_{1, s_1})(r_{2, s_2} - r_{2, s_3})} \right), \quad (11)$$

with the first subindex for r denoting a given component and the second denoting a given deformation or location –see (8). U is a step function such that $U(x) = 0$ if $x > 0$ and $U(x) = 1$ otherwise. Therefore, if β is large enough, the topology will be preserved. Topology preservation is ensured by the bilinear interpolation scheme adopted, which is justified in Appendix A. Nevertheless, this scheme only guarantees the continuity of the transformation and its inverse. For ensuring the differentiability of the transformation, a second-order interpolation scheme is required, in which case a larger neighborhood system would be necessary to simultaneously preserve the topology, with larger computational load [19]. Finally, note that the topology preservation is guaranteed in the composite transformation and not in the residual transformation corresponding to a given resolution level.

B. Optimization and parameter estimation

Once the field is completely designed, the remaining task is to establish a procedure for searching the optimal solution. Furthermore, the parameters in (7) have to be estimated or manually tuned (the latter is done in [9]). In this Section we describe an algorithm to optimize the field and jointly estimate its parameters. Its general flux for a given level l is presented in Fig. 3.

First, note that the Maximum Pseudo Likelihood Estimator (MPLE) is used to estimate the parameters of the prior. Assuming that for each iteration of the parameter estimation procedure the field variable \mathbf{x} is completely observed, the criterion for the ML estimation of the parameter λ , is

$$\lambda^* = \underset{\lambda}{\operatorname{argmax}} \Pi(\mathbf{x}; \lambda, \beta) = \underset{\lambda}{\operatorname{argmax}} \log(\Pi(\mathbf{x}; \lambda, \beta)). \quad (12)$$

This criterion requires the evaluation of the partition function $Z(\lambda, \beta)$, which is computationally intractable, as it involves a sum over the space of configurations of the field –see (5), which has a combinatorial number of elements. A common approximation is to use an approximate expression for the law Π :

$$\Pi(\mathbf{x}; \lambda, \beta) \simeq \prod_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \Pi(x_s | \mathbf{x}_{\delta(s)}; \lambda, \beta), \quad (13)$$

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 $\beta \leftarrow \infty$ 
 $\lambda \leftarrow 0$ 
 $\mathbf{x} \leftarrow \mathbf{0}$ 
 $\text{flag}_e \leftarrow 1$ 
while  $\text{flag}_e$  do
   $\sigma_j \leftarrow \text{MLE}_{\sigma_j}(f(F_0^j, F_1^j \mid \mathbf{x}; \sigma_j))$ 
   $\text{flag}_o \leftarrow 1$ 
  while  $\text{flag}_o$  do
     $\mathbf{x}' \leftarrow \mathbf{x}$ 
     $\mathbf{x} \leftarrow \text{ICM\_SWAP}(\Pi(\mathbf{x} \mid I_0, I_1; \sigma_0, \sigma_1, \lambda, \beta))$ 
    if  $H(\mathbf{x}) \geq H(\mathbf{x}') \vee |x_{\mathbf{s}} \neq x'_{\mathbf{s}}| < t_o |\mathcal{S}|$  then
       $\text{flag}_o \leftarrow 0$ 
    end if
  end while
   $\lambda' \leftarrow \lambda$ 
   $\lambda \leftarrow \text{MPLE}_{\lambda}(\Pi(\mathbf{x}; \lambda, \beta))$ 
  if  $|\lambda - \lambda'| < t_e$  then
     $\text{flag}_e \leftarrow 0$ 
  end if
end while

```

Fig. 3. Joint optimization and parameter estimation of the MRF.

that is, to express it as the product of the local conditional laws. This approximation generates the so called MPLE:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lambda^* &\simeq \underset{\lambda}{\operatorname{argmax}} \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}} \log(\Pi(x_{\mathbf{s}} \mid \mathbf{x}_{\delta(\mathbf{s})}; \lambda, \beta)) \\
 &= \underset{\lambda}{\operatorname{argmax}} \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}} \left[-\lambda \sum_{\mathcal{C}_2: (\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{s}') \in \mathcal{C}_2} V_2(x_{\mathbf{s}}, x_{\mathbf{s}'}) - \log \left(\sum_{z_{\mathbf{s}} \in \mathcal{K}} \exp(-H(z_{\mathbf{s}}, \mathbf{x}_{\delta(\mathbf{s})}; \lambda, \beta)) \right) \right], \tag{14}
 \end{aligned}$$

where the last identity is obtained by considering the prior terms in (7). Taking the derivative with respect to λ

$$\frac{\partial \log(\Pi(\mathbf{x}; \lambda, \beta))}{\partial \lambda} \simeq \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{\mathcal{C}_2: (\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{s}') \in \mathcal{C}_2} [-V_2(x_{\mathbf{s}}, x_{\mathbf{s}'}) + \sum_{z_{\mathbf{s}} \in \mathcal{K}} V_2(z_{\mathbf{s}}, x_{\mathbf{s}'}) \Pi(z_{\mathbf{s}} \mid \mathbf{x}_{\delta(\mathbf{s})}; \lambda, \beta)]. \tag{15}$$

The equation generated by equating this expression to zero has no closed form solution so it is solved iteratively. Specifically, we have made use of a gradient ascent procedure with a fixed gain factor³. The convergence of the procedure is controlled by a threshold t_e . When the absolute difference between two successive estimations of the parameter λ is smaller than t_e , the algorithm stops, as the parameters and the optimization have converged.

Second, the MLE can be used for the estimation of the parameters of the likelihood. It is formulated as

$$(\sigma_0^*, \sigma_1^*) = \underset{\sigma_0, \sigma_1}{\operatorname{argmax}} f(I_0, I_1 | \mathbf{x}; \sigma_0, \sigma_1) = \underset{\sigma_0, \sigma_1}{\operatorname{argmax}} \log(f(I_0, I_1 | \mathbf{x}; \sigma_0, \sigma_1)). \quad (16)$$

If one considers a likelihood model given by an exponential distribution in which, for analytical convenience, the intensity and gradient derived variables are assumed to be independent, as in the likelihood terms in (7),

$$f(I_0, I_1 | \mathbf{x}; \sigma_0, \sigma_1) = \prod_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{C}_1} \prod_j \sigma_j \exp\left(-\sigma_j V_1(x_{\mathbf{s}}; F_0^j, F_1^j)\right), \quad (17)$$

the MLE has a closed-form solution:

$$\sigma_j^* = \frac{|\mathcal{S}|}{\sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{C}_1} V_1(x_{\mathbf{s}}; F_0^j, F_1^j)}. \quad (18)$$

Finally, the parameter β is not estimated in the algorithm since it suffices to maintain its value large enough (tending to ∞) in order to preserve the topology.

Different techniques can be used to optimize the field for a given set of parameters. Due to the high complexity of the field, the optimizer selection has to pay attention to two major points:

- The variable to be optimized is not binary, but it is vector-valued and non-separable.
- The field includes high order interactions as given by the 3-element cliques which are not sparse.

In [7], a comparison is established among the main methodologies for the optimization of MRF with smoothness-based priors. The results obtained suggest a large improvement in performance when using modern optimization techniques such as GC or LBP with respect to classical techniques such as ICM. Nevertheless, the energy functions analyzed are based only on pairwise interactions between the variables of the field, so ternary interactions are not considered. Unfortunately, when dealing with ternary interactions, there are many cases in which the recent optimization techniques are not directly applicable or are computationally expensive [33] whereas the ICM algorithm [34] can be generally applied.

³This gain is set to 0.5 by inspecting the ascension dynamics.

In a draft version of the registration method included in this work [35], we have compared the efficiency of a set of GC-based optimizers against the ICM. Results show that, in spite of their improvement in performance, GC-based methods introduce a computational overload of at least 10^2 with respect to the ICM algorithm. Additionally, a test has been carried out for the interpolation problem presented here without significant improvement in performance of GC-based methods with respect to the ICM. Analogous considerations about this relative insensitivity of the interpolation results with respect to the energy minimum reached have also been reported in [4]. Hence, the insertion of modern optimization techniques has been judged inappropriate for this application and the ICM has been used instead. The input of the ICM algorithm is an initial configuration that corresponds to the null residual displacement. The convergence is controlled by a threshold t_o . When the number of changes in the local configurations of the field $|x_s \neq x'_s|$ (normalized by the number of sites $|\mathcal{S}|$) between two successive swaps of the ICM algorithm is smaller than t_o or the energy has not decreased, the optimization step finishes.

C. Implementation details

The interest of including this Section is twofold. On the one hand, it documents the configuration of parameters used in the method in order to assure the reproducibility of the algorithm. On the other hand, it summarizes the main computational requirements of the method together with some issues about the implementation adopted.

The parameters are included in Table I. Two levels of resolution are used. This way, the computation is accelerated and not much image structure is lost in the coarsest level, so the multiresolution strategy can successfully help the optimization to escape from local minima. The K value is the maximum value for which no significant loss in performance has been observed. The same can be said about t_0 and t_e . The rest of parameters are normalized to the image resolution. u_{\max} is in accordance with the value published in [4] for the maximum deformation. Small variations in the value of σ_M with respect to the one referred in Table I have minor impact in performance. As for ρ , its value is the same as the grid resolution of the field, which seems a reasonable assumption for capturing the maximum image information around each site with minimum overlap between blocks. Finally, the quantization step for the deformation is restricted by $\Delta_{\mathbf{k}}^0 < \Delta_{\mathbf{s}}^0$. These two parameters, the quantization step and the spacing of the grid of the field, together with the maximum deformation u_{\max} , are greatly application-dependent. Their selection must ensure the discretized field to be able to capture the range of deformations expected for the problem. Therefore, for small deformation estimation, u_{\max} should be accordingly small, as well as $\Delta_{\mathbf{k}}^0$ if fine details are to be recovered. The opposite occurs for large deformations, for which a multiresolution strategy could help

achieve the desired deformation resolution.

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF THE ALGORITHM.

$L = 2$	$\Delta_s^0 = 5\Delta_m^0$	$\Delta_k^0 = 2\Delta_m^0$	$u_{\max} = 16\Delta_m^0$	$K = 2$	$\sigma_M = \Delta_m^0$	$\rho = 5\Delta_m^0$	$t_0 = 0.02$	$t_e = 0.1$
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The algorithm presents a significant computational load. Its most demanding steps are summarized below (from the most to the least demanding) together with the strategy adopted to diminish their load:

- 1) **Implementation of the MPLE.** The high load of this step is related to the iterative gradient ascent procedure and the need of recomputing local expectations for each step [30]. The computation of local expectations is parallelized in order to diminish the load.
- 2) **Implementation of (9).** The load comes from the computation of image convolutions with a Gaussian kernel for each local configuration of the field. The computation is parallelized among different local configurations.
- 3) **Implementation of the ICM.** In this case, the main requirements are due to the computation of the energies for the local laws of the field [34]. A partially parallel visiting schedule is adopted in which the set of sites is partitioned into subsets of conditionally independent sites [36] so the elements of these subsets can be updated in parallel.

With all these improvements, the time needed for the registration of two 256×256 images has been of 11.20 s from which the MPLE algorithm has taken 6.36 s, the precomputation of the likelihood 1.64 s and the ICM algorithm 1.15 s. These computation times correspond to an execution on a $8 \times$ Dual Core AMD Opteron(tm) Processor 885 at 2.6 GHz (with cache size of 1 MB and shared memory of 16 GB).

Considering that the computational complexity of the method is primarily related to the estimation of the smoothness parameter λ , for those applications in which faster computation is required, one could resort to eliminate or manually tune the smoothness term, with a relatively small loss in performance (this is shown in Table III and Fig. 5). Other possibilities for acceleration could be to consider alternative multiresolution strategies or to simplify the likelihood terms in (9). Finally, it should be noticed that our method is intended to serve as a preprocessing step in order to reconstruct a feasible 3D representation of a given scene for subsequent image analysis. If the interpolation is used in real time applications such as scene rendering or interactive reformatting, it seems reasonable to try simpler and faster registration procedures for the registration step of the algorithm.

IV. INTERPOLATION

The registration algorithm as presented in Section III provides a transformation $\varphi_{0 \rightarrow 1}$. However, to improve the robustness of the result and to make the overall interpolation process unbiased with respect to the image roles, the correspondences are also calculated interchanging the fixed and moving images. This is implemented by extending the MRF with a set of sites located in the image 1 to compute $\varphi_{1 \rightarrow 0}$. Conditional independence is assumed for the variables of the field that refer to the transformations $\varphi_{0 \rightarrow 1}$ and $\varphi_{1 \rightarrow 0}$. Besides, the parameters of the MRF are jointly estimated for both transformations, so the sample of variables to compute the MLE and the MPLE is doubled in size. Therefore, all the equations of Section III are applicable to the extended set of sites.

Recall that the problem of registration-based interpolation is to determine the image $I_\tau(\mathbf{r}_\tau)$, which is located at a distance $\Delta_z \tau$ of the image I_0 , with Δ_z the distance between the input images I_0 and I_1 and $0 < \tau < 1$, based on the information provided by the deformation fields computed in the registration step. For that purpose, in our formulation, one must find four points $\mathbf{r}_{0,0}$, $\mathbf{r}_{1,1}$, $\mathbf{r}_{0,1}$ and $\mathbf{r}_{1,0}$, that correspond to the point \mathbf{r}_τ for the pair of images (first subindex) and the pair of transformations (second subindex). The intensities at these points are used to obtain the intensity at \mathbf{r}_τ . The problem of obtaining the corresponding points for a given \mathbf{r}_τ is illustrated in Fig. 4. They are computed as:

$$\mathbf{r}_{0,0} = \varphi_{0 \rightarrow \tau}^{-1}(\mathbf{r}_\tau) \quad \mathbf{r}_{1,1} = \varphi_{1 \rightarrow \tau}^{-1}(\mathbf{r}_\tau) \quad \mathbf{r}_{1,0} = \varphi_{0 \rightarrow 1}(\mathbf{r}_{0,0}) \quad \mathbf{r}_{0,1} = \varphi_{1 \rightarrow 0}(\mathbf{r}_{1,1}), \quad (19)$$

where

$$\varphi_{0 \rightarrow \tau}(\mathbf{r}) = \mathbf{r} + \tau \mathbf{u}_{0 \rightarrow 1}(\mathbf{r}) \quad \varphi_{1 \rightarrow \tau}(\mathbf{r}) = \mathbf{r} + (1 - \tau) \mathbf{u}_{1 \rightarrow 0}(\mathbf{r}), \quad (20)$$

which are invertible by the topology conservation of the registration method. In the case that the transformation is inverse-consistent, i.e., $\varphi_{1 \rightarrow 0}(\varphi_{0 \rightarrow 1}(\mathbf{r})) = \mathbf{r}$, the four points degenerate in two, which is handled naturally in our formulation.

Fig. 4. Interpolation problem. The method combines the intensities $I_0(\mathbf{r}_{0,0})$, $I_0(\mathbf{r}_{0,1})$, $I_1(\mathbf{r}_{1,0})$ and $I_1(\mathbf{r}_{1,1})$ to obtain $I_\tau(\mathbf{r}_\tau)$.

The interpolation combines the intensities of these four points to obtain $I_\tau(\mathbf{r}_\tau)$. To prevent from changes in the structures between the images, the influence of the points corresponding to each of the transformations $\varphi_{0 \rightarrow 1}$ and $\varphi_{1 \rightarrow 0}$ is weighed by the inverse of the information content [37] of the local distribution of the likelihood terms as

$$W_i[\mathbf{s}] = \left[-\log \left(\frac{\prod_{j=0}^1 f(F_i^j, F_{1-i}^j | x_{\mathbf{s}}; \sigma_j)}{\sum_{z_{\mathbf{s}} \in \mathcal{K}} \prod_{j=0}^1 f(F_i^j, F_{1-i}^j | z_{\mathbf{s}}; \sigma_j)} \right) \right]^{-1}, \quad (21)$$

with $i = \{0, 1\}$ indexing the weights for the transformations $\varphi_{0 \rightarrow 1}$ and $\varphi_{1 \rightarrow 0}$ respectively. Hence, if the data have a large information content given the local configuration (i.e., the local configuration has been selected even with a small data fidelity), these data are considered surprising for this configuration and therefore a small weight is assigned to the intensities derived from the corresponding transformation. Denoting $I_0^\tau = (1 - \tau)I_0$ and $I_1^\tau = \tau I_1$, the final interpolated image is obtained by

$$I_\tau(\mathbf{r}_\tau) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^1 W_i(\mathbf{r}_{i,i}) [I_i^\tau(\mathbf{r}_{i,i}) + I_{1-i}^\tau(\mathbf{r}_{1-i,i})]}{\sum_{i=0}^1 W_i(\mathbf{r}_{i,i})}, \quad (22)$$

with continuous weights and images being obtained by bilinear interpolation. Note that by setting $\mathbf{u} = 0$ in (20) and $W_i = 0.5$ in (22), a conventional linear interpolation is obtained.

Finally, regarding the computation times of the interpolation, the linear interpolation requires 0.04s whereas the interpolation step of the registration-based interpolation takes 0.53s for the images and computational environment described in Section III-C, so the computational overload of the registration-based interpolation may be feasible for many applications.

V. RESULTS

In order to validate the algorithm presented in this work two main experiments are accomplished. First, we perform a quantitative comparison with the state of the art literature in Section V-B. Second, we experimentally justify the inclusion of each of the main features and contributions of our method in Section V-C. The comparisons and justifications are established by following the methodology introduced in Section V-A. Finally, the advantages of performing a pre-registration step for interpolation are visually illustrated in Section V-D.

A. Validation methodology

In [10] a methodology was presented to evaluate the performance of interpolation methods. The idea is to compare the interpolated slice with the actual slice. The interpolation is performed by using the two adjacent slices with respect to the slice used for comparison. Different error measures with their respective statistical relevances computed by comparison of two interpolation methods were introduced as the basis of such methodology. The relevance r of the method m_1 with respect to the method m_2 for an error measure ERR is given by

$$r_{m_1/m_2}^{\text{ERR}} = \begin{cases} 100 \left(1 - \frac{\text{ERR}_{m_1}}{\text{ERR}_{m_2}} \right) & \text{if } \text{ERR}_{m_1} < \text{ERR}_{m_2} \\ -100 \left(1 - \frac{\text{ERR}_{m_2}}{\text{ERR}_{m_1}} \right) & \text{otherwise ,} \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

so positive relevance values imply that the method m_1 outperforms the method m_2 and the opposite occurs for negative values. Errors are averaged throughout the actual slices that can be interpolated by this procedure; that is, all the slices except for the first and the last in the sequence.

Results for some of these measures of error over a dataset that includes different tomographic imaging scenarios are presented in [4]. As advanced in Section II-B, MSD and NSD are used for comparison. These measures are expressed as:

$$\text{MSD} = \frac{1}{N_{\text{vox}}} \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{vox}}} (\hat{I}[\mathbf{m}_n] - I[\mathbf{m}_n])^2 \quad \text{NSD} = \frac{1}{N_{\text{vox}}} \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{vox}}} \nu(|\hat{I}[\mathbf{m}_n] - I[\mathbf{m}_n]|), \quad (24)$$

with N_{vox} the number of voxels over which the comparison is performed \hat{I} the interpolated image, I the actual image and ν a function such that $\nu(x) = 1$ if $x > 0.05I_{\text{max}}$ and $\nu(x) = 0$ otherwise, with I_{max} the maximum intensity value.

B. Comparison with other methods

Our results are compared with those published in [4], which in turn include their own results and those of [5]. The dataset for comparison includes four instances of each of the following image modalities: chest Computed Tomography (CT), head CT, chest MR and head MR, which have been made public in [4]. The different statistical relevance measures, averaged over the set of instances in each modality, are included in Table II. Overall results show that the method in [4] outperforms the method in [5] for the MSD whereas the opposite occurs for the NSD. Our method clearly outperforms both approaches in terms of the MSD whereas it slightly outperforms the best competing method in terms of the NSD for this dataset (for the sake of completeness, the MSD result reported in [28] on the head MR dataset is

31.5). Nevertheless, statistical tests comparing different methods are not included as the results for each data instance in the papers used for comparison are not at our disposal.

TABLE II

COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT APPROACHES FOR REGISTRATION-BASED INTERPOLATION. BEST RESULTS FOR EACH DATASET AND ERROR MEASURE ARE BOLDFACED. SUBINDEX *lin* REFERS TO LINEAR INTERPOLATION.

Relevance	CT chest	CT head	MR chest	MR head
$r_{[5]/lin}^{MSD}$	27.2	37.0	34.7	23.4
$r_{[4]/lin}^{MSD}$	31.2	43.8	34.7	28.1
$r_{ours/lin}^{MSD}$	34.5	51.0	37.7	33.9
$r_{[5]/lin}^{NSD}$	37.2	42.6	37.9	18.9
$r_{[4]/lin}^{NSD}$	35.4	40.3	27.9	15.9
$r_{ours/lin}^{NSD}$	37.3	42.5	40.1	23.8

C. Design validation

A series of statistical tests have been performed in order to justify the capability of the major features of our method to improve the interpolation performance. For these tests we use a sample of 43 cine echo-like steady-state free precession MR cardiac acquisitions performed inside a clinical environment of patients previously affected by an Acute Myocardial Infarction. The images have been acquired with a GE Genesis Signa 1.5T equipment. All of them have dimension 256×256 with a number of slices ranging from 12 to 17. Their resolution is $1.72 \times 1.72 \times 8 \text{ mm}^3$ with a slice thickness of 7 mm in one case and 6 mm in the remaining, so in all cases they present a certain slice gap. End-diastolic images were extracted for comparison. Echo time varies in the range 1.312 – 1.408 ms and repetition time varies in 3.256 – 3.444 ms, whereas flip angles are of 45° . The main reason to use this larger set of images instead of the one provided in [4], where only 4 images are available for each modality, is to improve the power of the statistical tests performed.

We compare the performance of the proposed method (referred in Table III as the general method —gen) for the MSD and NSD measures with respect to the following simplifications:

- Assuming that linear interpolation is performed, so $\mathbf{u} = 0$ and $W_i = 0.5$ (lin in the Table).
- Assuming that the structures are conserved between adjacent slices and thus not including the weights computed by (21), so $W_i = 0.5$.

- Assuming that $\beta = 0$, so no restriction for conservation of the topology is introduced in the field. This would be a way to compare our method to the approach in [9].
- Assuming that $\lambda = 0$, so no regularization is introduced in the field.
- Assuming that $\sigma_0 = 0$, so the intensity information is not included.
- Assuming that $\sigma_1 = 0$, so the gradient information is not included.
- Using the Mean Absolute Difference (MAD) metric; i.e., the denominator in (9) is removed.

The statistical significance of the general method with respect to each of these simplifications and error measures (t -test $p \leq 0.05$) and the corresponding statistical relevance, together with the mean Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) and results on a perceptual quality measure, the Universal Quality Index [38] (UQI), for each possible simplification are all included in Table III. From them, one can conclude that there is a strong evidence that the major features of our method introduce a significant improvement in performance as quantified by the NSD measure except for the case of the metric choice, which tends to worsen the performance. Regarding the MSD measure, the improvement is statistically significant for all features except for the inclusion of the inverse self-information weights, which seem not to alter the results. Finally, as for the UQI results, registration-based interpolation clearly overcomes linear interpolation and the best performance is obtained with the general method.

TABLE III

COMPARISON OF THE GENERAL METHOD OF REGISTRATION-BASED INTERPOLATION (GEN) WITH RESPECT TO DIFFERENT SIMPLIFICATIONS AND RESULTS FOR THE PSNR (IN DB) AND THE UQI MEASURES FOR EACH POSSIBLE SIMPLIFICATION.

Method	r^{MSD}	p^{MSD}	r^{NSD}	p^{NSD}	PSNR	UQI
gen/gen	0	—	0	—	28.819	0.918
gen/lin	51.06	$< 10^{-7}$	33.04	$< 10^{-7}$	25.566	0.815
gen/ $W_i = 0.5$	0.03	0.49	0.18	$< 10^{-7}$	28.818	0.918
gen/ $\beta = 0$	1.91	$< 10^{-7}$	1.41	$< 10^{-7}$	28.727	0.916
gen/ $\lambda = 0$	2.44	$< 10^{-7}$	2.02	$< 10^{-7}$	28.702	0.915
gen/ $\sigma_0 = 0$	1.89	$1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	3.67	$< 10^{-7}$	28.737	0.916
gen/ $\sigma_1 = 0$	1.25	$1 \cdot 10^{-7}$	1.78	$< 10^{-7}$	28.760	0.917
gen/MAD	0.93	$7 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-0.25	0.01	28.775	0.917

Finally, we show in Fig. 5 a comparison about the error measures obtained by the general procedure

Fig. 5. Relevance of the general method of registration (gen) with respect to a given manual selection of the parameters λ , σ_0 and σ_1 .

with respect to those obtained by fixing any of the estimated parameters, λ , σ_0 and σ_1 , to a predefined value along the optimization process. Results for λ show that the estimation introduces a positive or nearly null statistical relevance for both error measures in all the viable parameter ranges. For σ_0 , the estimation introduces a systematic performance improvement, specially for the NSD measure. Finally, for σ_1 , there is a range of values with negative statistical relevance, which is specially noticeable in the NSD measure, but in any case this worsening is slower than the improvement obtained by estimating σ_0 .

D. Visual results

In this Section we present a set of snapshots to verify and illustrate the capabilities of our interpolation method. To that end, as in previous Sections, we have computed the statistical relevance of our method when compared to the linear interpolator for the MSD and the NSD error measures, but in this case we consider its value referred only to each pair of adjacent images interpolated from the dataset of Section V-C and not averaged throughout the volume. The worst and best statistical relevance results for each error measure are $\min(r_{\text{ours/lin}}^{\text{MSD}}) = -30.35$, $\max(r_{\text{ours/lin}}^{\text{MSD}}) = 81.02$, $\min(r_{\text{ours/lin}}^{\text{NSD}}) = 9.83$, $\max(r_{\text{ours/lin}}^{\text{NSD}}) = 58.00$. Note that in the case of the MSD measure, the worst partial result of our method is worse than the linear interpolation one, but for the NSD measure our method always outperforms the linear interpolation. This is likely to be due to the fact that the registration is always able to find a large number of locally suitable matches between points and consequently to reduce the NSD measure, but, in extreme cases, the global underlying structural differences between the images are not reproduced accurately by the registration, so the MSD is worsened.

In Fig. 6 we show the case with the worst partial MSD results. Despite the larger MSD value, the visual appearance is better for the registration-based interpolation than for the linear interpolation as the

Fig. 6. Linear and registration-based interpolation for the worst case of the MSD measure. Left: linear interpolation. Center: real image. Right: registration-based interpolation.

Fig. 7. Linear and registration-based interpolation for the worst case of the NSD measure. Left: linear interpolation. Center: real image. Right: registration-based interpolation.

effect of double boundaries is considerably decreased, which can be appraised in the highest contrast of the image edges. The case with the worst partial NSD results for registration-based interpolation is shown in Fig. 7. The considerations about the image appearance are the same as in Fig. 6. Finally, in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, we show the interpolation pairs which present the best partial MSD and NSD results. In these cases, blurring in linearly interpolated images is even more pronounced. Particularly, in Fig. 6–9 it is noticeable the ability of registration-based interpolation to infer the location, or at least to maintain the contrast, of the torso boundary.

The spatial distribution of absolute errors between the interpolated and the actual images is shown in Fig. 10. Most significant error in the worst MSD case is located at the torso boundary. The main reason

Fig. 8. Linear and registration-based interpolation for the best case of the MSD measure. Left: linear interpolation. Center: real image. Right: registration-based interpolation.

Fig. 9. Linear and registration-based interpolation for the best case of the NSD measure. Left: linear interpolation. Center: real image. Right: registration-based interpolation.

for this could be the fact that this boundary does not deform in the plane of the images proportionally to the distance in the interpolating direction, so our method fails to reconstruct the underlying deformation. In the worst NSD case, the small improvement of registration-based interpolation is due to the fact that the number of outliers eliminated, though being small, is larger than the outliers that appear. As for the best MSD case, we can see that the linear interpolation errors are considerably decreased by the registration, particularly at the torso boundary. Finally, an important reduction of outliers is appraised in the best NSD case.

The reconstruction of 3D volumes is illustrated in Fig. 11. The results show a great improvement in the spatial coherence of the reconstructed slices by using our method. Nevertheless, for a proper spatial

Fig. 10. Spatial distribution of absolute errors of the linear and registration-based interpolated images for the best and worst cases of the MSD and NSD error measures. Upper row: linear interpolation. Lower row: registration-based interpolation. Cases from left to right: worst MSD, worst NSD, best MSD, best NSD.

representation of the left ventricular geometry, it is necessary to perform some kind of preprocessing for motion correction, as in other case a peaked myocardial boundary is observed along the long axis direction. A simple and fast algorithm is used for correction, which is included in the Appendix B. Furthermore, rendering by linear interpolation is able to diminish some sampling artifacts occurring at the edges of the image structures.

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a method to perform physically realistic registration of medical images in a stochastic discrete setting. In order to show its capabilities, we have applied the registration algorithm to help the interpolation of largely spaced tomographic slices. The results show that our method outperforms state of the art registration schemes used previously for interpolation in a dataset shared for evaluation in [4]. This suggests that, though generally outperforming intensity-based interpolation methods, the actual benefits of a registration-based interpolation approach are strongly dependent on the registration method on which it is based, so more work is needed to find more suitable registration algorithms for this problem. Research on this field has the advantage that the relative performance of new and existing registration algorithms can be easily evaluated by following the methodology in [10]. Nonetheless, the

Fig. 11. Reconstruction of 3D volumes. From top to bottom: original long-axis image, image reconstructed with our method and image reconstructed with additional breath motion correction. From left to right: screen rendering by nearest-neighbor interpolation and by linear interpolation.

proposed registration method can be applied to other image analysis problems, in particular to those in which the topology preservation is relevant to obtain realistic solutions.

Besides the improvement in performance with respect to other works, the major attributes of our algorithm have proven to increase the performance of the method for interpolation of short axis acquisitions in cardiac MR images and the results have shown to be visually realistic. The major drawback of the algorithm is the high complexity. Hence, in Section III-C, some potential acceleration strategies have been proposed.

3D extension of the algorithm is straightforward except for the extension of the topology-preserving condition in (11). This presents some computational issues if a rectilinear grid is going to be used, as the set of 4 conditions of positivity of the Jacobian computed over 3-element cliques becomes a set of 64 conditions of positivity computed over 4-element cliques for each element of the grid (see [19] for the details). Hence, in order to perform this extension efficiently, a tetrahedral grid should be used or a relaxed topology-preserving restriction should be considered.

With respect to the optimization procedure, we have resorted to the classical ICM as opposed to more modern algorithms. The reason is the slight improvement in the registration step while the computation complexity increases dramatically at the resolution levels we have worked. However, for other application

domains or other resolutions, these methods could be of great interest.

APPENDIX A

TOPOLOGY PRESERVATION FOR BILINEAR INTERPOLATION OF DEFORMATION FIELDS

In this Appendix we derive the conditions that a deformation field defined on the vertices of a square has to fulfill in order to preserve the topology for all points inside the square under bilinear interpolation. Without loss of generality, we can assume the unit square given by $\mathbf{r}_1 = (0, 0)$, $\mathbf{r}_2 = (1, 0)$, $\mathbf{r}_3 = (1, 1)$ and $\mathbf{r}_4 = (0, 1)$. The deformation $\varphi(\mathbf{r}) = (\varphi_1(\mathbf{r}), \varphi_2(\mathbf{r}))$ of a point $\mathbf{r} = (r_1, r_2)$ inside the square under bilinear interpolation of the deformation is given by

$$\varphi(\mathbf{r}) = (1 - r_1)(1 - r_2)\varphi^1 + r_1(1 - r_2)\varphi^2 + r_1r_2\varphi^3 + (1 - r_1)r_2\varphi^4, \quad (25)$$

where $\varphi^i = \varphi(\mathbf{r}_i)$ denotes the deformation at point \mathbf{r}_i , with $1 \leq i \leq 4$. The Jacobian of this transformation is

$$J(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\partial\varphi_1(\mathbf{r})}{\partial r_1} \frac{\partial\varphi_2(\mathbf{r})}{\partial r_2} - \frac{\partial\varphi_1(\mathbf{r})}{\partial r_2} \frac{\partial\varphi_2(\mathbf{r})}{\partial r_1}, \quad (26)$$

which, plugging (25) and after some algebraic manipulations, is transformed into:

$$J(\mathbf{r}) = (1 - r_1)(1 - r_2)J^1 + r_1(1 - r_2)J^2 + r_1r_2J^3 + (1 - r_1)r_2J^4, \quad (27)$$

that is, the bilinear interpolation of the approximations to the Jacobian at the vertices, J^i , by taking finite differences using the current vertex and the two adjacent vertices of the square (i.e. the points of the triangle for which the right angle is subtended by the vertex \mathbf{r}_i):

$$\begin{aligned} J^1 &= (\varphi_1^2 - \varphi_1^1)(\varphi_2^4 - \varphi_2^1) - (\varphi_2^2 - \varphi_2^1)(\varphi_1^4 - \varphi_1^1) \\ J^2 &= (\varphi_1^2 - \varphi_1^1)(\varphi_2^3 - \varphi_2^2) - (\varphi_2^2 - \varphi_2^1)(\varphi_1^3 - \varphi_1^2) \\ J^3 &= (\varphi_1^3 - \varphi_1^4)(\varphi_2^3 - \varphi_2^2) - (\varphi_2^3 - \varphi_2^4)(\varphi_1^3 - \varphi_1^2) \\ J^4 &= (\varphi_1^3 - \varphi_1^4)(\varphi_2^4 - \varphi_2^1) - (\varphi_2^3 - \varphi_2^4)(\varphi_1^4 - \varphi_1^1). \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

It is clear that a necessary condition for $J(\mathbf{r}) > 0$ is $J^i > 0 \forall 1 \leq i \leq 4$. Moreover, it is also a sufficient condition, because $J(\mathbf{r})$ is a convex sum of the 4 Jacobian approximations [19].

APPENDIX B

ALGORITHM FOR CORRECTION OF MOTION DUE TO RESPIRATION

A simple and fast algorithm is used for correction of interslice motion due to patient respiration. Suppose that we are given a set of slices I_n , with $n = \{1, \dots, N\}$. Then, the algorithm proceeds as stated in Fig. 12.

```

 $\mathbf{u}_n^0 \leftarrow \text{REG}(I_n, I_{n-1})$ 
 $\mathbf{u}_n^1 \leftarrow \text{REG}(I_n, I_{n+1})$ 
 $v \leftarrow 0$ 
while  $v < V$  do
   $\mathbf{t}_n = 0.5(\mathbf{u}_n^0 + \mathbf{u}_n^1)$ 
   $\hat{n} = \underset{n \in \{2, \dots, N-1\}}{\text{argmax}} (|\mathbf{t}_n|)$ 
   $I_{\hat{n}} \leftarrow \text{TRA}(I_{\hat{n}}, \mathbf{t}_{\hat{n}})$ 
   $\mathbf{u}_{\hat{n}+1}^0 \leftarrow \mathbf{u}_{\hat{n}+1}^0 + \mathbf{t}_{\hat{n}}$ 
   $\mathbf{u}_{\hat{n}-1}^1 \leftarrow \mathbf{u}_{\hat{n}-1}^1 + \mathbf{t}_{\hat{n}}$ 
   $\mathbf{u}_{\hat{n}}^0 \leftarrow \mathbf{u}_{\hat{n}}^0 - \mathbf{t}_{\hat{n}}$ 
   $\mathbf{u}_{\hat{n}}^1 \leftarrow \mathbf{u}_{\hat{n}}^1 - \mathbf{t}_{\hat{n}}$ 
   $v \leftarrow v + 1$ 
end while

```

Fig. 12. Algorithm for correction of interslice motion due to respiration.

The function REG translationally registers two adjacent images by minimizing their Mean Squared Difference (in the formulation given in Fig 12, in any case, preventing the index n to go out of range) and outputs the estimated translation for all the images indexed by n . Then, the algorithm iterates V times to improve the alignment among the slices. First, it detects the worst aligned image. Second, it corrects this image by the function TRA that translates the image to better align with the two adjacent slices. Third, it updates the translation parameters in accordance with the new alignment.

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